

EMPLOYEE'S POSITIVE PERSONALITY TRAITS: DO THEY MATTER FOR THEIR EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE THROUGH PSYCHOLOGICAL CAPITAL? AN INTEGRATIVE DIMENSIONAL STUDY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20712138>

Keywords

Positive personality traits,
Emotional intelligence,
Psychological capital.

Article History

Received: 03 July 2025

Accepted: 15 August 2025

Published: 30 August 2025

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Abstract

The quality of administrative staff is widely regarded as a key asset for organizational development. Constructs such as emotional intelligence, positive personality traits, and psychological capital are considered critical in enhancing employee effectiveness. This study aimed to examine the association of positive personality traits to emotional intelligence and its dimensions through psychological capital. Particular emphasis was placed on understanding how university administrative employees utilize their psychological resources to achieve emotional intelligence, an area that has received limited attention in the context of Pakistan. Data were collected from 330 administrative staff members across three universities using a stratified random sampling technique. The findings revealed that psychological capital mediates the relationship among four positive personality traits and four components of emotional intelligence, although mediation was not observed uniformly across all constructs. Positive personality traits namely "extraversion, agreeableness, openness to experience, and conscientiousness" emerged as significant predictors of psychological capital. Furthermore, psychological capital demonstrated a strong association with important dimensions of emotional intelligence, including "self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship management". Overall, the results support the hypothesis that psychological capital serves as a mediating mechanism among positive personality traits and employee emotional intelligence. The study concludes with implications and recommendations for future research.

INTRODUCTION:

The concept of personality traits has been widely explored in psychological literature, with early discussions linking it to individual differences reflected in language and behavior (Goleman, 1997). "Personality traits refer to enduring patterns of thoughts, emotions, and behaviors that characterize individuals and shape their responses to various situations" (Srivastava &

John, 1999). The Five-Factor Model (FFM) is one of the key prominent frameworks for understanding personality, "identifying five core dimensions: extraversion (e.g., sociable and energetic), agreeableness (e.g., cooperative and compassionate), conscientiousness (e.g., organized and dependable), openness to experience (e.g., creative and intellectually curious), and neuroticism" (Soto & Jackson,

2013). Personality plays a fundamental role in the adaptation process, influencing how individuals cope with life challenges. Research indicates that individuals with more negative or pessimistic personality tendencies are more likely to experience psychological distress, whereas those with positive traits tend to report better mental health outcomes (Torgersen & Vollrath, 2000). Over recent decades, the Big Five model has gained substantial empirical support and is widely regarded as a reliable and valid framework for assessing personality traits (John, 1990). In particular, positive personality dimensions such as “extraversion, openness to experience, agreeableness, and conscientiousness” have been identified as important predictors of adaptive functioning and well-being.

Psychological capital (PsyCap) originated within the fields of economics and sociology as a construct aimed at understanding performance and behavior in organizational settings. Early perspectives emphasized its role in shaping employees’ confidence and expectations, thereby influencing workplace outcomes (William et al, 1997). This conceptualization later evolved into the notion of positive psychological capital within the broader framework of positive organizational behavior. Psychological capital integrates key theoretical perspectives, including positive psychology, which highlights individual strengths and potential; positive organizational behavior; and elements of human and social capital encompassing what individuals know who they know, and who they are (Carolyn & Fred, 2004). It is also viewed as an investment in human development that can enhance performance and contribute to competitive advantage. In essence, psychological capital represents a positive psychological state characterized by core components such as “self-efficacy, hope, optimism, and resilience”, which collectively support individual growth and effective performance in organizational contexts.

Emotional intelligence manifests in diverse forms, reflecting individual differences in cognitive and affective capabilities. Some individuals excel in particular types of mental tasks, while others demonstrate strengths in

different domains, indicating variability in human abilities. While certain individuals appear to perform effectively across multiple areas, others exhibit more specialized competencies, with distinct strengths exceeding others (McCrae & Costa, 1992). Emotions, as emphasized in the literature, are integral to human functioning and encompass subjective experiences that range from immediate affective states to enduring emotional dispositions and long-term mood patterns (Erasmus, 2007). An individual conceptualize emotional intelligence through “self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship management” (Goleman, 2001).

The present study is significant in that it addresses a gap in the literature by examining the interrelationships among psychological capital, personality traits, and emotional intelligence. It specifically investigates how administrative staff with diverse personality profiles utilizes their psychological capital to understand and regulate emotions, as well as to achieve professional objectives. By focusing on higher education institutions, the study offers a novel perspective on the role of personality and emotional intelligence within this context. The research identifies the dominant positive personality traits among university administrative staff and compares the effects of key traits “extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and openness to experience” on psychological capital. It further examines the influence of psychological capital on emotional intelligence and evaluates its intervening role in positive personality traits and emotional intelligence association. Notably, the study highlights which positive personality traits are most effective in enabling individuals to manage workplace diversity, teamwork, and organizational challenges. It also demonstrates how psychological capital, in conjunction with emotional intelligence, enhances employees’ awareness and regulation of their emotions, thereby contributing to more effective workplace functioning.

Literature review:**Positive Personality traits:**

The Five-Factor Model (FFM) of personality is a widely accepted framework that explains individual differences through five core dimensions. Developed through trait-based approaches, this model focuses on identifying, classifying, and organizing similarities and differences in personality characteristics. It provides a systematic method for understanding stable and enduring patterns of behavior that influence how individuals respond to various situations (Poropat, 2009). "The FFM offers a comprehensive yet concise representation of personality by encompassing five relatively independent dimensions: extraversion, conscientiousness, agreeableness, neuroticism, and openness to experience" (Ebru, 2018). Among these, positive personality traits such as "openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, and agreeableness" are particularly important in explaining adaptive behavior and effective functioning (Therasa & Vijayabanu, 2015). These personality dimensions are considered universal and play a significant role in shaping employee behavior and performance in organizational settings (Szostek, 2021; Udin & Yuniawan 2020). Overall, the Five-Factor Model provides a robust framework for understanding how personality traits influence individual differences and workplace outcomes.

Openness to experience reflects a personality dimension characterized by broad interests, creativity, intellectual curiosity, and sensitivity to inner feelings (McCrae, 1987). It represents an individual's willingness to embrace new ideas and adapt to novel situations (Christensen, 2023). Agreeableness refers to the extent to which individuals are cooperative, compassionate, and harmonious in their interactions with others (Eisenberg & Graziano, 1997). Individuals high in agreeableness are typically described as kind, trusting, tolerant, and warm, often holding a positive view of human nature, individuals are more inclined to help others even in less favorable circumstances (Tobin & Graziano, 2002). "Extraversion represents an energetic approach toward the social and material world

and includes traits such as sociability, activity, assertiveness, and positive emotionality" (Olivr et al, 2008). Highly extraverted individuals are generally more active, enthusiastic, and motivated (Seibert & Zhao, 2006). Conscientiousness, on the other hand, denotes traits such as organization, reliability, and goal orientation (McCrae & Costa, 1992). Individuals high in conscientiousness tend to be disciplined, responsible, and achievement-oriented, whereas those low in this trait often struggle with motivation and task completion (Goleman, 1997). Extensive research identifies conscientiousness as a strong predictor of job performance and workplace effectiveness (Pletzer & Abrahams 2025), as such individuals are more deliberate, persistent, and committed to achieving their goals (George & Zhou, 2001). Overall, these personality traits play a significant role in shaping individual behavior, motivation, and performance across various contexts.

Emotional intelligence and its dimensions

Emotional intelligence (EI) is conceptualized as a trait-like construct reflecting inherent tendencies that support individual well-being and effective functioning. It encompasses a range of emotional self-perceptions that are rooted in lower-order personality traits. "Over time, researchers have developed various measurement approaches to assess EI, typically distinguishing between personal and social competencies. Personal competencies include self-awareness and self-management, while social competencies comprise social awareness and relationship management" (Rhee et al, 2000; Singh, 2010). The mixed model of emotional intelligence views EI as a broad set of capabilities and skills that enhance individual and organizational performance. According to Goleman, (1995), emotional intelligence plays a central role in leadership effectiveness, as managing emotions is fundamental to successful organizational functioning. This model is structured around four core dimensions "self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship management" (Magnus, 2006). Overall, emotional intelligence integrates personal and

social competencies that enable individuals to understand, control, and effectively employ emotions not only in personal context, but also in professional domain.

Self-Awareness:

Self-awareness is widely regarded as the foundational component of emotional intelligence, as it enables individuals to recognize and understand their own emotional states (Salovey & Mayer, 1995). It involves awareness of one's strengths, weaknesses, and the impact of emotions on behavior (Alferaih, 2022). In organizational contexts, self-awareness is considered a critical competency that underpins effective emotional functioning in the workplace (Yeung, 2009). Emotional intelligence, popularized in the business domain by Goleman, (2001), has been recognized as a key factor in enhancing managerial effectiveness and organizational performance. It is increasingly viewed as more influential than purely cognitive abilities in managing workplace dynamics (Agwu, 2015). Within this framework, self-awareness represents the initial step in developing emotional intelligence, as it allows individuals to accurately perceive their emotions and understand their consequences. Individuals with high self-awareness are better able to regulate their behavior, build strong interpersonal relationships, and perform effectively in their roles. They possess clarity about their emotions, can anticipate how their actions affect others, and are more capable of channeling their emotional states toward achieving personal and professional goals.

Self-management

"Self-management refers to the ability to control or redirect disruptive impulses and moods and the propensity to suspend judgment and think before acting" Daniel Goleman (2001). It involves consciously managing one's emotional responses to sustain motivation and effective functioning in various situations. More broadly, self-management also encompasses the capacity of individuals to handle life challenges, including managing symptoms, treatments, lifestyle

adjustments, and psychosocial outcomes, particularly in the context of health and well-being (Wilkinson & Whitehead, 2009). Scholarly consensus suggests that self-management applies not only to health-related contexts but also to broader domains such as personal development and workplace functioning, where it plays a crucial role in enhancing performance, adaptability, and overall well-being (Fitzwater & Jerant, 2005).

Social awareness

"Social awareness represents another key dimension of emotional intelligence, referring to an individual's ability to recognize and understand the emotions of others, including interpreting nonverbal cues and social signals" (Goleman, 1995, 1998). Individuals with high levels of social awareness are better equipped to respond appropriately in interpersonal situations and maintain effective social interactions. Empirical evidence suggests that greater social awareness is associated with lower levels of depressive symptoms (Dugan, 2006). Moreover, it contributes positively to life satisfaction by reducing negative emotional states such as fatigue, hopelessness, and pessimism, while enhancing social interaction, critical thinking, and emotional regulation (Celik, 2016). Overall, social awareness plays a significant role in promoting psychological well-being and improving the quality of interpersonal relationships.

Relationship-management

Relationship management represents the final dimension of emotional intelligence, As per Daniel Goleman (2001) "Relationship management is the ability to inspire, influence, and develop others while managing conflict and fostering teamwork and collaboration." It involves fostering positive interactions and maintaining constructive relationships in social and organizational settings. In leadership contexts, relationship management is oriented toward enhancing interpersonal harmony and emotional well-being, ensuring that individuals feel valued and supported within the work

environment. Unlike task-focused management, which emphasizes goal attainment, relationship management prioritizes the development of trust, collaboration, and a positive social climate among team members (Northouse, 2004). conclusively, relationship management is essential for promoting effective communication, strengthening interpersonal bonds, and facilitating a supportive and cohesive work environment.

Psychological capital:

“Psychological capital is conceptualized as a positive psychological state of an individual, comprising four key components: self-efficacy, optimism, hope, and resilience. Self-efficacy reflects an individual’s confidence in taking on challenges and exerting effort to achieve goals. Optimism involves maintaining positive expectations regarding present and future success. Hope refers to the ability to set goals and identify alternative pathways to achieve them, particularly when obstacles arise. Resilience enables individuals to persevere and recover from difficulties in pursuit of desired outcomes”. In contemporary organizational contexts, psychological capital is recognized as a valuable resource that contributes to competitive advantage and enhanced performance (Youssef, & Luthans, 2007). It represents a set of positive psychological capacities that can be developed to improve employee effectiveness and organizational outcomes. Given the increasing complexity and competitiveness of modern workplaces, strengthening employees’ psychological resources has become essential for adapting to changing demands. Empirical evidence indicates that employees who embrace higher psychological capital are more inclined to complete tasks efficiently and report greater satisfaction with their work environment (Pradhan & Jena, 2015). Overall, psychological capital plays a crucial role in fostering employee well-being, motivation, and performance in organizational settings.

Theoretical frame work

Relationship of positive personality traits to psychological capital

Timothy & Coomer, (2016) model examines the relationships of personality traits with psychological capital as a mediating variable. Empirical evidence indicates that “honesty-humility and extraversion” are positively related to psychological capital, while grit also shows a strong positive association with psychological capital. In turn, psychological capital demonstrates a positive relationship with job performance. Further research has explored the direct effects of personality traits, particularly “extraversion and conscientiousness”, on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) among university teachers, while also considering the moderating role of psychological capital. Findings suggest that extraversion positively predicts OCB; however, psychological capital moderates this relationship by weakening the strength of the positive association between extraversion and OCB (Syed et al, 2018).

Existing literature provides limited but growing evidence on the relationship between psychological capital and personality traits. Research indicates a positive association between psychological capital and openness to experience, which also contributes to enhanced organizational commitment (Ebru, 2018). Further studies highlight that personality traits significantly influence psychological well-being, particularly in challenging contexts such as entrepreneurship. Extraversion has been found to be positively related to psychological well-being, while psychological capital plays a mediating role in this relationship. Additionally, openness to experience is positively associated with psychological capital, which in turn supports better psychological outcomes (Kreeti & Satishchandra, 2017).

According to Ebru, (2018) the impact of psychological capital and personality traits on organizational commitment, an area that has received relatively limited empirical attention. Findings indicate a positive association between psychological capital and conscientiousness, which in turn is linked to higher levels of

organizational commitment. Moreover, another study examined whether teachers' personality traits serve as significant predictors of their psychological capital. A strong and positive relationship revealed between conscientiousness and psychological capital, suggesting that this personality trait plays a significant role in enhancing individuals' psychological resources (Hasan, 2017).

As entrepreneurs confront increasing challenges, their psychological well-being is influenced not only by external demands but also by individual personality characteristics. Empirical evidence suggests that personality traits play a significant role in shaping psychological well-being, with this relationship further mediated by factors such as psychological capital. Specifically, extraversion has been found to be positively associated with psychological well-being, while psychological capital mediates the relationship between personality traits such as agreeableness and well-being outcomes (Kreeti & Satishchandra, 2017). Additionally, research examining the interplay between anxiety, the Big Five personality traits, and psychological capital indicates that agreeableness is negatively associated with anxiety symptoms and positively related to psychological capital. In contrast, neuroticism shows a positive relationship with anxiety and a negative association with psychological capital (Lie & Meng, 2015).

Relationship of psychological capital to emotional intelligence and its dimensions

Sarwar et al, (2017) examine the emotional intelligence intervening role on the effect of psychological capital to project success. The findings indicate that psychological capital is

significantly associated with emotional intelligence, which in turn positively influences project success. Additionally, psychological capital shows a strong positive relationship with self-awareness, a key component of emotional intelligence. Further evidence suggests that enhancing emotional intelligence through continuous assessment and developmental interventions can improve employees' psychological well-being, both directly and indirectly through the mediating role of psychological capital. Psychological capital has also been found to exert a significant positive effect on subjective well-being and is closely linked with self-awareness among employees (Saravi-Moghadam et al., 2016).

In words of Eylem & Hakkı, (2016) the relationship between emotional intelligence and psychological capital, recognizing both constructs as important indicators of individual capability from different perspectives. As relatively recent concepts, emotional intelligence and psychological capital have been associated with a range of positive outcomes in both professional and personal contexts. Emotional intelligence, understood as an individual's capacity for adaptive and intelligent behavior, is closely linked with psychological capital, which represents a set of positive psychological resources utilized in professional settings. Empirical findings indicate a strong positive association between emotional intelligence and employees' psychological capital. Furthermore, psychological capital demonstrates a direct and significant relationship with the relationship management dimension of emotional intelligence (Lisete & Nathalia, 2013; Luiza et al., 2006).

Research framework model

Research hypothesis:

H₁: Positive Personality traits have significant positive effect on employee's psychological capital.

H_{1a}: Openness to experience has significant positive effect on psychological capital.

H_{1b}: Agreeableness has significant positive effect on employee's psychological capital.

H_{1c}: Extraversion has significant positive effect on employee's psychological capital.

H_{1d}: Conscientiousness has significant positive effect on employee's psychological capital.

H₂: Psychological capital has significant positive effect on employee's emotional intelligence.

H_{2a}: Psychological capital has significant positive effect on self-awareness.

H_{2b}: Psychological capital has significant positive effect on self-management.

H_{2c}: Psychological capital has significant positive effect on social-awareness.

H_{2d}: Psychological capital has significant positive effect on relationship management.

H₃: Psychological capital mediates the relationship among each employee's positive personality traits to each dimension of their emotional intelligence.

Research methodology

This study is grounded in an epistemological perspective, which defines what constitutes valid and acceptable knowledge within the research

domain. It adopts a positivist philosophy, a stance aligned with the natural sciences that emphasizes the objective measurement of observable phenomena. Positivism assumes that social reality can be examined through empirical observation and that research should aim to generate generalizable, law-like findings. Accordingly, the study relies on objective, quantitative data, which are considered more reliable and suitable for testing hypotheses and establishing causal relationships.

The study is descriptive and empirical and target population will be admin staff of public sector institution of higher education in Quetta The analysis of the research will be mainly measurable. Deductive method will be used. The study will be conducted. Positive personality traits and with its dimensions emotional intelligence with its four main dimensions and psychological capital is the mediating variable of this research. The questionnaire will have organized measure queries with set answers in mandate to compute the association between variables. To get desired information, data will be collected through questionnaires .330 staff members were selected as sample size for data by applying computing method by (Yamane, 1967). Stratified random sampling technique will be employed.

In this study, each of the four subscales was drawn from reputable scales previously published,

tested and used in recent place of work studies. More specifically, the personality traits items were developed (Goldberg, 1993). The personality Traits questionnaire, also refer to “as the (FFM), consist of 19 items it has four scales Openness to experience, Extraversion, Agreeableness and Conscientiousness”, each measured by six items. The emotional intelligence items were derived from (Goleman, 2001) and short scale of five items of psychological capital (Miklós et al, 2024) will be adapted. All constructs are measured on a 5-point Likert scale which range from “1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree)”. Multiple regression data analysis techniques will be used to

test hypotheses. SPSS version 23 will be used for data analysis computation.

Results of the study:

Out of 330 questionnaires were distributed from which 274 questionnaires was received. Response rate was 93%. Measure contains three variables with their dimensions which contain the cronbach’s alpha value, mean and standard deviation of understudy constructs are shown in the table.

Cronbach alpha values are greater than 0.60 which establish consistency of items under each scale.

Table 1 exhibits Reliability statistics results

Constructs	Cronbach Alpha Value	Number of items
Extraversion	.62	4
Agreeableness	.61	4
Conscientiousness	.64	4
Openness to experience	.71	3
Psychological capital	.72	5
Self-awareness	.61	4
Self-management	.60	4
Social-awareness	.61	4
Relationship management	.62	3

Table 2 showing Correlation among variables, their Mean and standard deviation

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Extraversion	1								
Agreeableness	0.99**	1							
Conscientiousness	0.37**	0.37**	1						
Openness to experience	0.52**	0.51**	0.76**	1					
Psychological capital	0.31**	0.31**	0.76**	0.66**	1				
Self-awareness	0.99**	0.99**	0.38**	0.51**	0.32**	1			
Self-management	0.88**	0.89**	0.39**	0.46**	0.35**	0.89**	1		
Social-awareness	0.87**	0.88**	0.40**	0.46**	0.35**	0.89**	0.99**	1	
Relationship - Management	0.49**	0.49**	0.47**	0.46**	0.40**	0.49**	0.50**	0.50**	1
Mean	3.26	3.28	3.58	3.44	3.52	3.27	3.26	3.27	3.46
Standard deviation	.78	.77	.69	.86	.70	.76	.76	.77	.83

** . “Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)”

Table 3 showing Multiple regression statistics results

Relationships among variables	B	P	R ²
Positive Personality traits → Psychological Capital	.69	.000	.47
Psychological Capital → Emotional intelligence	.43	.000	.18
Psychological Capital → Self-awareness	.35	.000	.12
Psychological Capital → Self-management	.35	.000	.12
Psychological Capital → Social-awareness	.36	.000	.13
Psychological capital → Relationship management	.48	.000	.23

The result exhibits significant positive effect of positive personality traits” extraversion, agreeableness, openness to experience, and conscientiousness” on psychological capital ($\beta=.69, p < .05$) and psychological capital significantly positively influence emotional intelligence ($\beta=.43, p < .05$). Furthermore, all positive personality traits bring 47 % variance in psychological capital and psychological capital brings 18% change in emotional intelligence.

Examination was lead among psychological capital and four dimensions of emotional intelligence which reveals that psychological capital significantly predicted emotional intelligence dimensions: psychological capital shows significant positive impact on self-awareness ($\beta =.35, p < .05$) with variance of 12%, self-management ($\beta =.35, p < .05$) with variance of 12%, social awareness ($\beta =.36, p < .05$) with variance of 13%, and relationship management ($\beta=.48, p < .05$) with variance of 23%.

Table 4 showing mediation statistics results

Positive personality traits and intelligence dimensions	Emotional	Direct effect		Indirect effect			
		Path C		Path A		Path B	
		B	P	B	P	B	P
Openness to experience	→ Self-awareness	.47	.00	.78	.00	.64	.04
Openness to experience	→ Self-management	.48	.00			.49	.05
Openness to experience	→ Social-awareness	.48	.00			.41	.02
Openness to experience	→ Relationship management	.54	.00			.17	.11
Extraversion	→ Self-awareness	.98	.00	.36	.00	.11	.41
Extraversion	→ Self-management	.98	.00			.22	.05
Extraversion	→ Social-awareness	.97	.00			.24	.02
Extraversion	→ Relationship management	.54	.00			.36	.00
Agreeableness	→ Self-awareness	.95	.00	.42	.00	.40	.04
Agreeableness	→ Self-management	.94	.00			.30	.01
Agreeableness	→ Social-awareness	.94	.00			.01	.63
Agreeableness	→ Relationship management	.58	.00			.32	.00
Conscientiousness	→ Self-awareness	.35	.00	.81	.00	.22	.02
Conscientiousness	→ Self-management	.36	.00			.23	.01
Conscientiousness	→ Social-awareness	.37	.00			.24	.01
Conscientiousness	→ Relationship management	.52	.00			.24	.01

Mediating Variable: Psychological capital

The results in Table 4 demonstrate a significant indirect effect of openness to experience to psychological capital ($\beta = .78, p < .05$) and psychological capital to self-awareness ($\beta = .64, p < .05$) and significant direct effect of openness to experience on self-awareness ($\beta = .47, p < .05$), a significant indirect effect of openness to experience to psychological capital ($\beta = .78, p < .05$) and psychological capital to self-management ($\beta = .49, p < .05$) and significant direct effect of openness to experience on self-management ($\beta = .48, p < .05$), a significant indirect effect of

openness to experience to psychological capital ($\beta = .78, p < .05$) and psychological capital to social-awareness ($\beta = .41, p < .05$) and significant direct effect of openness to experience on social-awareness ($\beta = .48, p < .05$), a significant indirect effect of openness to experience to psychological capital ($\beta = .78, p < .05$) and in significant effect of psychological capital to relationship management ($\beta = .17, p > .05$) and significant direct effect of openness to experience on relationship management ($\beta = .54, p < .05$). Furthermore table exhibits significant indirect effect of extraversion on psychological capital (β

=.36, $p < .05$) and psychological capital to self-awareness ($\beta = .11$, $p > .05$) and significant direct effect of extraversion on self-awareness ($\beta = .98$, $p < .05$), a significant indirect effect of extraversion to psychological capital ($\beta = .36$, $p < .05$) and psychological capital to self-management ($\beta = .22$, $p < .05$) and significant direct effect of extraversion on self-management ($\beta = .98$, $p < .05$), a significant indirect effect of extraversion to psychological capital ($\beta = .36$, $p < .05$) and psychological capital to social-awareness ($\beta = .24$, $p < .05$) and significant direct effect of extraversion on social-awareness ($\beta = .97$, $p < .05$), a significant indirect effect of extraversion to psychological capital ($\beta = .36$, $p < .05$) and psychological capital to relationship management ($\beta = .36$, $p < .05$) and significant direct effect of extraversion on relationship management ($\beta = .54$, $p < .05$).

Additionally, A significant indirect effect of agreeableness on psychological capital ($\beta = .42$, $p < .05$) and psychological capital to self-awareness ($\beta = .40$, $p < .05$) and significant direct effect of agreeableness on self-awareness ($\beta = .95$, $p < .05$), a significant indirect effect of agreeableness to psychological capital ($\beta = .42$, $p < .05$) and psychological capital to self-management ($\beta = .30$, $p < .05$) and significant direct effect of agreeableness on self-management ($\beta = .94$, $p < .05$), a significant indirect effect of agreeableness to psychological capital ($\beta = .42$, $p < .05$) and insignificant effect of psychological capital to social-awareness ($\beta = .01$, $p > .05$) and significant direct effect of agreeableness on social-awareness ($\beta = .94$, $p < .05$), a significant indirect effect of agreeableness to psychological capital ($\beta = .42$, $p < .05$) and psychological capital to relationship management ($\beta = .32$, $p < .05$) and significant direct effect of agreeableness on relationship management ($\beta = .58$, $p < .05$).

Notably, a significant indirect effect of conscientiousness on psychological capital ($\beta = .81$, $p < .05$) and psychological capital to self-awareness ($\beta = .22$, $p < .05$) and significant direct effect of conscientiousness on self-awareness ($\beta = .35$, $p < .05$), a significant indirect effect of conscientiousness to psychological capital ($\beta = .81$, $p < .05$) and psychological capital

to self-management ($\beta = .23$, $p < .05$) and significant direct effect of conscientiousness on self-management ($\beta = .36$, $p < .05$), a significant indirect effect of conscientiousness to psychological capital ($\beta = .81$, $p < .05$) and psychological capital to social-awareness ($\beta = .24$, $p < .05$) and significant direct effect of conscientiousness on social-awareness ($\beta = .37$, $p < .05$), a significant indirect effect of conscientiousness to psychological capital ($\beta = .81$, $p < .05$) and psychological capital to relationship management ($\beta = .24$, $p < .05$) and significant direct effect of conscientiousness on relationship management ($\beta = .52$, $p < .05$).

All findings demonstrate partial mediation of psychological capital among all above mentioned relationships.

Discussion

This study examined the interrelationships among emotional intelligence and its dimensions, psychological capital, and positive personality traits, with three hypotheses receiving empirical support. The findings indicate a significant association between personality dimensions and psychological capital and aligned with earlier research. In particular, extraversion demonstrated a strong positive relationship with psychological capital, suggesting that individual's string in sociability and adaptability are more evident to utilize effective coping strategies (Watson & Clark, 1997; Seibert & Zhao, 2006; McCrae & Costa, 1994). These results reinforce the central role of extraversion within personality frameworks and its contribution to positive psychological resources. Furthermore, "openness to experience, agreeableness, and conscientiousness" were all found to be positively related to psychological capital. Individuals high in agreeableness tend to be cooperative and supportive, as well as concerned with fairness and interpersonal care, which enhances their psychological resources (Tobin & Graziano, 2001) similarly, conscientiousness showed a significant positive association, indicating that disciplined and goal-oriented individuals possess higher levels of psychological capital (Mount & Barrick, 1991; Aftab et al, 2018). Overall, the

findings suggest that positive personality traits serve as important predictors of psychological capital and emotional intelligence, aligning with prior research (Youssef, & Luthans, 2007).

The findings also support a significant and positive relationship between psychological capital and emotional intelligence, thereby confirming the second hypothesis. All four dimensions of emotional intelligence were found to be positively associated with psychological capital, indicating that employees with higher emotional capabilities tend to possess stronger psychological resources. In particular, the experience of positive emotions was directly linked to higher levels of psychological capital, suggesting that individuals who frequently experience positive affect are more likely to demonstrate optimism, resilience, and efficacy (Tjimuku, et al, 2025). Moreover, the results highlight that “key components of emotional intelligence such as self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship management” are strongly connected with psychological capital. High self-acceptance and self-esteem contribute to enhanced psychological resources (Emmons, 2000; Dulewicz & Higgs, 2000). Additionally, relationship management was found to have a particularly strong association with psychological capital (Avolio et al., 2007). Overall, these findings reinforce the view that emotional intelligence dimensions play a critical role in developing and sustaining psychological capital.

The third hypothesis aimed to examine the psychological capital mediating role in the relationship of personality traits to emotional intelligence. The findings support the mediation hypothesis, indicating a statistically significant improvement in the relationship between the independent and dependent variables when the mediating variable is included, consistent with the approach proposed by Baron & Kenny (1986). These results contribute meaningfully to the existing literature, particularly within the context of Pakistan, and extend broader discussions in organizational psychology. Notably, these relationships had not previously been

examined in the context of Quetta, highlighting the study’s contextual significance.

Conclusion

Personality traits in the workplace can be understood as behavioral tendencies that enhance individuals’ self-awareness while also improving their sensitivity to others’ emotions, thereby facilitating social adjustment and interpersonal harmony. This study examines the relationships among employee’s positive personality traits, their psychological capital, and emotional intelligence dimensions in higher education sector of Quetta. Data were analyzed using correlation and stepwise regression techniques to assess the statistical associations among variables. The findings reveal a significant positive relationship between personality traits and emotional intelligence, with emotional intelligence treated as the dependent variable. Additionally, positive personality traits are positively associated with psychological capital, which in turn shows a strong positive relationship with emotional intelligence among administrative staff. Moreover, psychological capital is positively linked to all dimensions of emotional intelligence: “self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship management”. Mediation analysis indicates that psychological capital partially mediates the relationship among positive personality traits and emotional intelligence dimensions between extraversion, conscientiousness, and emotional intelligence.

Strength, Limitation, and Future research recommendation

The findings make a meaningful contribution to the literature, particularly within the Pakistani context, while also informing broader debates in organizational psychology. Notably, prior research has rarely examined the combined relationships among employee’s positive personality traits, psychological capital, and emotional intelligence its respective dimensions. The results suggest that these associations may reflect generalizable psychological processes rather than context-specific phenomena, indicating their relevance

across diverse cultural and organizational settings. Furthermore, the study provides empirical support for the reliability of three psychometric scales within the Pakistani context, strengthening their applicability in future research. A key and original contribution of this work is the identification of psychological capital as a mediating mechanism between positive personality traits and emotional intelligence, offering deeper insight into how these constructs interact within organizational environments.

Despite its contributions, few limitations exist. The research was conducted within a constrained timeframe of eight months, which may have limited a more in-depth exploration of the variables. The sample was restricted to administrative staff from only three public universities in Quetta and application of convenience sampling technique, thereby limiting findings generalization to other institutions or regions. Additionally, a cross-sectional design, was employed and data was collected at a single point in time, which restricts the ability to draw causal inferences; a longitudinal approach would be more appropriate for establishing causality. The self-reported questionnaires increase the possibility of response bias. Finally, limited resources further constrained the study, particularly in terms of geographic coverage, as data collection was confined to a single city.

This study was confined to three universities in Quetta, which limits the scope of its applicability. Future research is recommended to extend this work to other sectors, such as the health and police departments, using diverse samples while examining the same variables. Similar studies may also be conducted in other cities of Pakistan and across different countries to enhance external validity. Comparative research between major cities within Pakistan could further enrich understanding of contextual differences. Additionally, the research model may be expanded by incorporating variables such as gender as a potential mediator. The study also recommends expanding future research by examining additional mediating or moderating variables to better understand the relationships

among personality traits. Although the present study focused on public universities, future investigations could include private institutions and other organizational sectors to broaden the generalizability of the findings.

Implication of the study

The study underscores the role of personality traits in influencing emotional intelligence, indicating that enhancing these qualities can improve organizational behavior and institutional effectiveness within higher education in Quetta. It suggests that structured personality development and emotional skills training for both staff and students can help create a more progressive academic environment and support the development of positive character attributes. Additionally, it is recommended that organizations prioritize recruiting administrative staff with higher psychological capital and emotional intelligence to effectively manage workforce emotions and contribute to organizational success.

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